

Pathological Properties of Weak L^p Spaces

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Abstract

Weak L^p spaces, that are shown through this paper by L^p_w , are function spaces that are closed to L^p spaces, but somehow larger. The question that we are going to partially answer in this paper, is that how much it is larger. Actually we prove that $L^p_w(\mathbb{R}) \setminus L^p(\mathbb{R}) \cup \{0\}$ contains an infinitely generated algebra.

Keywords: Algebrability; Lineability; Pathological Properties; Weak L^p .

1. Introduction

Weak L^p spaces are function spaces that are closely related to L^p spaces. We do not know the exact origin of Weak L^p spaces. The Book by Colin Bennett and Robert Sharpley [1] contains a good presentation of Weak L^p but from the point of view of rearrangement function. In the present paper we first study the Weak L^p space from the point of view of distribution function. This circumstance motivated us to undertake a preparation of the present paper containing a detailed exposition of these function spaces. Then we proceed to the main theorem that proves the existence of an infinitely generated vector space in $Weak L^p [0,1] \setminus L^p [0,1] \cup \{0\}$. A subset M of a vector space X is called lineable in X if $M \cup \{0\}$ contains an infinite dimensional vector space. In this setting, authors in [2] have proved that $Weak L^p [0,1] \setminus L^p [0,1]$ is lineable in $Weak L^p [0,1]$. What we are going to prove here is that $L^p_w(\mathbb{R}) \setminus L^p(\mathbb{R}) \cup \{0\}$ contains an infinitely generated algebra. This last property is called Algebrability.

The origin of lineability is due to Gurariy ([5, 6]) that showed that there exists an infinite dimensional linear space such that every non-zero element of which is a continuous nowhere differentiable function on $\mathcal{C}[0; 1]$. Many examples of vector spaces of functions on \mathbb{R} or \mathbb{C} enjoying certain special properties have been constructed in the recent years. More recently, many authors got interested in this subject and gave a wide range of examples. For more results on lineability we refer the reader to [3].

Throughout this paper (X, Ω, μ) is a measure space and \mathbb{F} is \mathbb{R} or \mathbb{C} .

1. 1 Definition. For $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{F}$ a measurable function on X , the distribution function of f is the function D_f defined on $[0, \infty)$ as follows

$$(1) \quad D_f(\lambda) := \mu(\{x \in X: |f(x)| > \lambda\}).$$

The distribution function D_f provides information about the size of f but not about the behavior of f itself near any given point. For instance, a function on \mathbb{R}^n and each of its translates have the same distribution function. It follows from 1. 1 that D_f is a decreasing function of λ (not necessarily strictly).

Let (X, Ω, μ) be a measurable space and f and g be measurable functions on X then D_f enjoys the following properties.

- (1) $|g| \leq |f|$ μ - a. e. implies that $D_g \leq D_f$;
- (2) $D_{cf}(\lambda) = D_f\left(\frac{\lambda}{|c|}\right)$ for all $c \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$ and $\lambda \in [0, \infty)$;
- (3) $D_{f+g}(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2) \leq D_f(\lambda_1) + D_g(\lambda_2)$ for all $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in [0, \infty)$;
- (4) $D_{fg}(\lambda_1 \lambda_2) \leq D_f(\lambda_1) + D_g(\lambda_2)$ for all $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in [0, \infty)$;

For more details on distribution function see [4] and [7].

Next, Let (X, Ω, μ) be a measurable space, for $0 < p < \infty$, we consider

$$\text{Weak } L^p := \left\{ f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{F}: \exists c > 0 \forall \lambda > 0, D_f(\lambda) \leq \left(\frac{c}{\lambda}\right)^p \right\}.$$

We will use the notation L_w^p to show *Weak* L^p . Observe that $L_w^\infty = L^\infty$.

1. 2 Proposition. Let $f \in L_w^p$ with $0 < p < \infty$. Then

$$\|f\|_{L_w^p} := \inf \left\{ c > 0: D_f(\lambda) \leq \left(\frac{c}{\lambda}\right)^p \text{ for all } \lambda \in (0, \infty) \right\} = \left(\sup_{\lambda > 0} \lambda^p D_f(\lambda) \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = \sup_{\lambda > 0} \lambda \{D_f(\lambda)\}^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

Proof. Let us define

$$\alpha = \left\{ c > 0: D_f(\lambda) \leq \left(\frac{c}{\lambda}\right)^p \text{ for all } \lambda \in (0, \infty) \right\},$$

and

$$\beta = \left(\sup_{\lambda > 0} \lambda^p D_f(\lambda) \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

Since $f \in L_w^p$, so there exists $c > 0$ such that

$$D_f(\lambda) \leq \left(\frac{c}{\lambda}\right)^p, \lambda \in (0, \infty).$$

Therefore

$$\left\{ c > 0: D_f(\lambda) \leq \left(\frac{c}{\lambda}\right)^p \text{ for all } \lambda \in (0, \infty) \right\} \neq \emptyset.$$

On the other hand

$$\lambda^p D_f(\lambda) \leq \beta^p,$$

thus $\{\lambda^p D_f(\lambda): \lambda > 0\}$ is bounded above by β^p and $\beta \in \mathbb{R}$. Therefore

$$(2) \quad \alpha = \left\{ c > 0: D_f(\lambda) \leq \left(\frac{c}{\lambda}\right)^p \text{ for all } \lambda \in (0, \infty) \right\} \leq \beta.$$

Now, let $\varepsilon > 0$, then there exists $c > 0$ such that $\alpha \leq c \leq \alpha + \varepsilon$ and

$$D_f(\lambda) \leq \left(\frac{c}{\lambda}\right)^p \text{ for all } \lambda \in (0, \infty),$$

and thus

$$\lambda^p D_f(\lambda) \leq c^p \leq (\alpha + \varepsilon)^p, \lambda \in (0, \infty).$$

Then

$$\sup_{\lambda > 0} \lambda^p D_f(\lambda) \leq (\alpha + \varepsilon)^p.$$

Therefore

$$\left(\sup_{\lambda > 0} \lambda^p D_f(\lambda) \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \leq \alpha + \varepsilon.$$

Since $\varepsilon > 0$ is arbitrary so $\beta \leq \alpha$. This completes the proof. \square

By this norm, we can redefine L_w^p spaces in the form of L^p spaces.

1. 3 Definition. Let (X, Ω, μ) be a measure space. For $0 < p < \infty$ the space L_w^p is defined as the set of all μ -measurable \mathbb{F} -valued functions f such that

$$\inf \left\{ c > 0: D_f(\lambda) \leq \left(\frac{c}{\lambda}\right)^p \text{ for all } \lambda \in (0, \infty) \right\} < \infty.$$

Two functions in L_w^p will be considered equal if they are equal μ -a. e.

For $0 < p < \infty$, L_w^p is larger than L^p . We obtain this result in the next proposition and remark.

1. 4 Proposition. For any $0 < p < \infty$, $L^p \subset L_w^p$ and for any $f \in L^p$ we have

$$\|f\|_{L_w^p} \leq \|f\|_{L^p}.$$

Proof. If $f \in L^p$, then for any $\lambda > 0$, D_f we have

$$\lambda^p \mu(\{x \in X: |f(x)| > \lambda\}) \leq \int_{|f(x)| > \lambda} |f|^p d\mu \leq \int_X |f|^p d\mu = \|f\|_{L^p}^p.$$

Therefore

$$(3) \quad \mu(\{x \in X: |f(x)| > \lambda\}) \leq \left(\frac{\|f\|_{L^p}}{\lambda}\right)^p.$$

Next from 3 we have

$$\left(\sup_{\lambda > 0} \lambda^p D_f(\lambda) \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \leq \|f\|_{L^p}.$$

This shows that

$$\|f\|_{L_w^p} \leq \|f\|_{L^p}.$$

□

1. 5 Remark. The inclusion in the previous proposition is strict. Indeed let $f(x) = x^{-\frac{1}{p}}$ on $(0, \infty)$ with the Lebesgue measure. For any $\lambda > 0$ we have

$$m \left(\left\{ x \in (0, \infty) : \frac{1}{|x|^{\frac{1}{p}}} > \lambda \right\} \right) = m \left(\left\{ x \in (0, \infty) : |x| < \frac{1}{\lambda^p} \right\} \right) = 2\lambda^{-p}.$$

Thus $f \in L_w^p(0, \infty)$ but

$$\int_0^\infty \left(\frac{1}{x^{\frac{1}{p}}} \right)^p dx = \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{x} dx \rightarrow \infty.$$

So $f \notin L^p$.

2. Main Result

In this section we prove that $L_w^p(\mathbb{R}) \setminus L^p(\mathbb{R}) \cup \{0\}$ contains an infinitely generated algebra. First we present the definition of algebraability and two facts about norm of L_w^p .

2. 1 Definition. Let A be a subset of an algebra L . A is called algebraable in L if $A \cup \{0\}$ contains an infinitely generated subalgebra W of L .

2. 2 Proposition. Let $f, g \in L_w^p$. Then

$$(1) \|cf\|_{L_w^p} = |c| \|f\|_{L_w^p}, \text{ for any constant } c,$$

$$(2) \|f + g\|_{L_w^p} \leq 2 \left(\|f\|_{L_w^p}^p + \|g\|_{L_w^p}^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

Proof.(1) For $c > 0$ we have

$$\mu(\{x \in X : |cf(x)| > \lambda\}) = \mu(\{x \in X : |f(x)| > \frac{\lambda}{c}\}),$$

thus

$$D_{cf}(\lambda) = D_f\left(\frac{\lambda}{c}\right).$$

Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \|cf\|_{L_w^p} &= \left(\sup_{\lambda > 0} \lambda^p D_{cf}(\lambda) \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = \left(\sup_{\lambda > 0} \lambda^p D_f\left(\frac{\lambda}{c}\right) \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} = \left(\sup_{c\lambda > 0} c^p w^p D_f(w) \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ &= c \left(\sup_{cw > 0} w^p D_f(w) \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}. \end{aligned}$$

So

$$\|cf\|_{L_w^p} = c \|f\|_{L_w^p}.$$

(2) Note that

$$\{x \in X: |f(x) + g(x)| > \lambda\} \subseteq \left\{x \in X: |f(x)| > \frac{\lambda}{2}\right\} \cup \left\{x \in X: |g(x)| > \frac{\lambda}{2}\right\}.$$

Hence

$$\mu\{x \in X: |f(x) + g(x)| > \lambda\} \leq \mu\left(\left\{x \in X: |f(x)| > \frac{\lambda}{2}\right\}\right) + \mu\left(\left\{x \in X: |g(x)| > \frac{\lambda}{2}\right\}\right).$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda^p D_{f+g}(\lambda) &\leq \lambda^p D_f\left(\frac{\lambda}{2}\right) + \lambda^p D_g\left(\frac{\lambda}{2}\right) \leq 2^p \left[\sup_{\lambda>0} \lambda^p D_f(\lambda) + \sup_{\lambda>0} \lambda^p D_g(\lambda) \right] \\ &= 2^p \left[\|f\|_{L_w^p}^p + \|g\|_{L_w^p}^p \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\|f + g\|_{L_w^p} = \left(\sup_{\lambda>0} \lambda^p D_{f+g}(\lambda) \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \leq 2 \left[\|f\|_{L_w^p}^p + \|g\|_{L_w^p}^p \right]^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

□

The previous proposition shows that L_w^p is a vector space and that $\|\cdot\|_{L_w^p}$ is a quasi-norm on it (which is a functional that is like a norm except that it does only satisfy the triangle inequality with a constant $c \geq 1$, that is $\|f + g\| \leq c(\|f\| + \|g\|)$.)

To proceed to the main theorem, we need the following lemma.

2. 3 Lemma. If $I \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ has finite Lebesgue measure, then χ_I , the characteristic function of I , belongs to L_w^p for all $0 < p < \infty$.

Proof. For all $\lambda > 0$ we have

$$m(\{x \in \mathbb{R}: |\chi_I(x)| > \lambda\}) = \begin{cases} 0, & \lambda > 1 \\ m(I), & 0 < \lambda \leq 1 \end{cases}.$$

Thus

$$\|\chi_I\|_{L_w^p} = \left(\sup_{\lambda>0} \lambda^p D_{\chi_I}(\lambda) \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \leq (m(I))^{\frac{1}{p}}.$$

So $\chi_I \in L_w^p$. □

2. 4 Theorem. $L_w^p(\mathbb{R}) \setminus L^p(\mathbb{R})$ is algebraable in $L_w^p(\mathbb{R})$, for all $0 < p < \infty$.

Proof. Let $0 < p < \infty$ be fixed. Define $f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} |x|^{-\frac{1}{p}}, & \text{if } x \neq 0, \\ 0, & \text{if } x = 0 \end{cases}$$

For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ let $g_n = \chi_{[0, \frac{1}{n}]}$. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ be fixed. By the argument after Proposition 2. 2, $(f \cdot g_n)^m \in L_w^p(\mathbb{R})$ for all $n, m \in \mathbb{N}$.

On the other hand by remark 1. 5, $(f \cdot g_n)^m \notin L^p(\mathbb{R})$. Since for each $i, j \in \mathbb{N}$ with $i < j$, $m\left(\left[0, \frac{1}{i}\right] \setminus \left[0, \frac{1}{j}\right]\right) \neq 0$, so for each $i, j \in \mathbb{N}$ with $i < j$, $f \cdot g_j \neq f \cdot g_i$.

Therefore $\{(f.g_n)^m : m, n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is an infinite set. Again by the argument after Proposition 2.2 and above reasoning, the algebra generated by $\{(f.g_n)^m : m, n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ is a subset of $L_w^p(\mathbb{R}) \setminus L^p(\mathbb{R}) \cup \{0\}$. So $L_w^p(\mathbb{R}) \setminus L^p(\mathbb{R})$ is algebraable. \square

2. 5 Remark. This trend of research seems to be very broad. One can ask about the cardinality of the generators of the algebra contained in $L_w^p(\mathbb{R}) \setminus L^p(\mathbb{R}) \cup \{0\}$. Another question that can be considered is that whether there exists an infinitely generated free algebra of functions contained in $L_w^p(\mathbb{R}) \setminus L^p(\mathbb{R}) \cup \{0\}$ or not. Also changing the space \mathbb{R} by a general measure space would contribute to new results.

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